

ON A NEW OCCURRENCE OF *CONUS TYPHON* KILBURN, OFF THE MOÇAMBIQUE COAST

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Conus typhon KILBURN, 1974 is a well known, albeit uncommon species, found along South East African coasts.

It is a moderately variable species, ranging from the typical pattern of fine brown spiral lines on a pale background to grayish violaceous banded specimens and also occasional totally white shells.

It is regularly found by shrimp trawlers in relatively shallow water (10 to 40 meters).

It may prove useful to quote from the original description:

“Shell orthoconic (...) shoulder angular, non-carinate; spire low, coeloconic, usually rather mamillate but with a sharp apex, whorls moderately stepped; shoulder slope concave, bearing very fine spiral striae, crossed by growth lines which in places may be so coarse as to render both suture and shoulder undulating (...) Colouration variable. (...) Periostracum thin, close, rather transparent, deciduous; smooth, save for fine growth-lamellae on shoulder slope”.

Quite recently, however, a distinct population has been found.

It comes from much deeper water than the ones previously known: specimens are being collected from a depth of 118 meters, in a restricted area off Quissico, South Moçambique, on a muddy sand bottom.

The first striking feature about this new population is the average size of the specimens: whereas the previously known shallow water specimens are usually between 30 and 50 mm long, the ones under discussion are much bigger, easily attaining 100 mm (it is worth noticing that the “world size record” for *C. typhon* KILBURN, given by WAGNER & ABBOT 1990, is fixed at 55.4 mm).

This fact in itself would be of some interest, given that the large size appears to be rather constant in this population.

But another interesting feature is observed in the structure of the periostracum: whereas in typical (shallow water) specimens the periostracum is always smooth, no variations whatsoever having been recorded, the deep water specimens show, in the instances where it was preserved, a distinct periostracum, because it has several rows of hairy tufts.

In the illustrated specimen, we counted as many as 7 rows of tufts.

This is an interesting observation in itself, since the periostracum is generally assumed to be constant for each species and we have indeed found almost no refe-

rences to periostracum variation within a species, in the literature available to us (exceptions being: R. M. FILMER, "*Conus adami* WILS, 1988 - species or subspecies" (in press), where it is mentioned that *C. trigonus* REEVE, 1848 may show two forms of periostracum, one with tufts on the spire whorls only, the other with tufts on the body whorl, and also *C. quercinus* LIGHTFOOT, 1786, which can present a thin a pale periostracum or else a very thick and dark one (form *albonerosa* GARRARD, 1966), according to R. M. FILMER). But that same observation also raises further problems, as we are about to see.

As a matter of fact, it is generally accepted that *C. typhon* KILBURN can be related to the Australian *C. nielsenae* MARSH, 1962. In the original description, separation is established on the following grounds:

"*C. nielsenae* MARSH, 1962, from Queensland, may show a pattern of similar spiral lines, but is rather closer to *C. bayani* in shape and its periostracum is not smooth as in *C. typhon*, but bears spiral rows of bristles".

Now, if we look at the original description of *C. nielsenae* MARSH, we find that the periostracum is described as "thin, semi-transparent, encircled with rows of projecting hair-like tufts — COOMANS & FILMER (1985), indicate it as smooth, but that was quite probably an oversight (R. M. FILMER, pers. com.).

The suggestion is obvious: whereas the shallow water populations of *C. typhon* KILBURN constantly present the morphological features of the shell which distinguish it from *C. nielsenae* MARSH and at the same time have a smooth periostracum, the deep water form still retains the same shell morphology, but shares with *C. nielsenae* MARSH the hairy structure of the periostracum.

Another species in this complex merits comparison with *C. typhon* KILBURN, namely *C. reductaspiralis* WALLS, 1979. Originally described as a subspecies of *C. nielsenae* MARSH, it was later raised to a species (COOMANS & FILMER, 1985).

C. reductaspiralis WALLS occurs off North West Australia, in the Indian Ocean and is thus geographically closer to the locality of *C. typhon* KILBURN. *C. reductaspiralis* WALLS has the same shape as *C. typhon* KILBURN, lacking the elongated and waisted shape of *C. nielsenae* MARSH. Although very variable in colour and markings, specimens with the fine brown spiral lines are not uncommon. In addition, there are frequently brown markings on the spire similar to but darker than those on *C. typhon* KILBURN. The periostracum is somewhat thicker and has a number of closeknit ridges becoming obsolete towards the shoulder. *C. reductaspiralis* WALLS usually but not always possesses a brown to orange stain at the base, not present in *C. typhon* KILBURN.

We find that too little is known of the relative importance of these characteristics and their meaning to allow us to present any taxonomical conclusions arising from the mentioned facts.

The similarity in periostracum structure certainly brings the new population of *C. typhon* KILBURN closer to *C. nielsenae* MARSH. At the same time, the distinct habitat and larger size also separate the newly found specimens from the previously known populations of *C. typhon* KILBURN.

It would be easy to speculate that *C. typhon* KILBURN may turn out to be the same species as *C. nielsenae* MARSH, occurring in two different subspecies (as suggested by WALLS (1978): “[*C. nielsenae* is] very similar to *C. typhon*, which should perhaps be considered a South African subspecies.”), but we do not at the moment feel justified to do so. What is more, we do not think that such a suggestion would serve any real taxonomical purpose. So, we prefer to state the facts as we know them, hoping that they will encourage further research on the identity of the two *taxa* involved and also on the role the periostracum structure in specific diagnosis.

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Fig. 1 — *Conus typhon* Kilburn (deep water form)

Fig. 2 — *C. typhon* Kilburn, specimen with periostracum

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

